

Mobile Application for Diseases Self-Diagnosis during Pandemic

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Abstract. In the times of pandemics, it becomes difficult to communicate between doctors and patients. This could be either due to doctors are busy treating disease conditions caused by the pandemic, there are not enough places in hospitals that may be filled with patients, or patients fear to be one of the victims of this pandemic. To find a solution in such exceptional circumstances, this study suggests a cognitive platform that allows people to be self-diagnose by comparing their medical symptoms with symptoms for certain diseases. This system can also improve the accuracy of the diagnosis by sending medical cases and self-diagnose results to specialist doctors to do confirmation or make an update to the diagnosis. Preliminary results show a promising contribution and benefits to healthcare organizations and professionals. However, as a project in its infancy, there is a believe that there are many features needs to be added to provide comprehensive, accurate and more beneficial healthcare services.

Keywords: Self-Diagnosis, ICT, Telemedicine, Epidemics, Healthcare App

1 Introduction

Increasingly, technology has started changing the landscape of the world. The emerging role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has created a huge impact on many of our sectors such as business, industry, healthcare, entertainment and many more. While considering healthcare, the role of ICT has assisted in many areas such as enhancing the quality of care, increases the patient security and data protection, and reduces operating and administrative cost, to name a few.

Providing live demographic information, deep statistics, and computer-based simulations are just a few examples on how ICT could help to overcome unusual circumstances.

Current ICT-based health services are adequate when there is no exceptional scenario such as disease outbreak. As when such scenario arises, nations are expecting more from ICT professionals and solution providers to help them overcome, in a variety of ways, the outbreak faster with lowest losses.

With the emergence of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) in December 2019, the world's attention has shifted toward fighting the virus and stopping its spreading. Until today, nations, communities, healthcare companies are still struggling against this global pandemic caused by the virus. As by the time of writing this work, the death toll rises to over five-hundred thousand people with over 25 million of infected people worldwide [1] and the number is still continuously increasing with every minutes.

At the beginning of the outbreak, one of the most important dilemmas that facing healthcare teams as they try to contain the disease, is to track who was in contact with infected people for the past days (14 days is recommend in most cases) [2].

However, with increased number of infected people, hospitals have exceeded their limits, which creates another dilemma. In county like Iraq, with limited number of hospitals and medical equipment, it is difficult now to occupy and admit all number of patients. On the other hand, it became hard and risky for patients with other medical conditions to visit hospital.

These situations must inspire researchers to pave a way for opportunities where doctors can still practice their job without exposing themselves or their patients to additional risk. While patients should still receive medical advice especially those with chronic medical conditions.

With current advances of handheld devices, high quality sensors, and wide usage of smartphones, makes these devices a perfect tool for achieving and delivering different services [3]. The only thing that could magnitude their potential is the software component or apps. Unfortunately, in a county like Iraq, there is no infrastructure for app-based services for health sector.

The rest of this work is organized as follows: in section 2, the role of mobile application in healthcare is presented along with possible potential opportunities. Section 3 represents the contribution of this work, which explains the usage of mobile application for early and self-diagnosis when typical patient-to-doctor diagnosis became problematic. Section 4 holds the testing scenarios for the proposed system along with the preliminary results. Finally, section 5 concludes the presented work and pave the way for possible future enhancements.

2 The Role of Mobile Application in healthcare

ICT plays an important role in improving health care for individuals and societies [4]. By providing new and effective ways of accessing, communicating, and storing information. With the ever-evolution of ICT, now its role can provide services that are more

sophisticated. With emergence of handheld such as smartphones, these services can give a real-time information per individual with respect to their geographical location.

Mobile smartphones have proved to be a great tool for tracking people activities [5]. With granted permissions, mobile applications, apps for short, will have the rights to access person's location through the attached GPS, accessing cameras, as well as accessing other sensors and hardware to gather a considerable amount of data [6].

By utilizing these sensors and hardware, while process the gathered data, different potential healthcare services and information will see the light [7]. Measuring heartbeat rate, recording people walking and running distances, are just few straightforward examples to what is possible to achieve.

Mobile application developers, along with consultations from healthcare professionals can even go beyond that and target special healthcare needs. Technology, particularly mobile applications, can help families to track and observe their loved ones. For instance, people diagnosed with Alzheimer have no way to know where they came from and how to get back to their homes. With an application installed on their smartphones, their families will have the ability to track their movements and will have the ability to be notified by the app if the person has gone beyond his/her safe zone [8].

At a larger scale, organizations, communities and nations, may request for an assist from ICT professionals, to develop a unified platform to deliver, for instance, important health and safety related messages and instructions, where sometime, these messages and instructions could customize according to the geographical area and health conditions of recipients [9].

All these works have approached a single path solution that is either relying on an automated system or just maintain a platform for communication among individuals and authorities. These single path solutions suffer either from inaccuracy due to their fully automated system or lack of potential services since they reply on human interaction only. Integration of both paths will potentially magnify the benefits of these services and solution for the healthcare sector.

In conjunction with the current COVID-19 pandemic, there were several noticeable ICT-driven initiatives. Unfortunately, there was not much to mention at the scale of Iraq. In an online survey targeted healthcare professionals in Iraq, several have highlighted that lack of E-health services have added insult to the injury during the COVID-19 pandemic. On the other hand, centralized demographic and health-related information are gather in manual old-fashioned manner.

3 Mobile Application for Diseases Early Diagnosis

Leveraging the potential of embedded sensors of smartphones for self and early diagnosing is used in many studies [10-14]. Current smartphones are equipped with high-end sensors such as cameras, speakers, microphones, GPS, and heartbeat sensors. These sensors are a great at capturing data with a high precision. Most of these systems relies on self or auto diagnosing only. These systems are good for giving immediately diagnosing. However, to magnify the potential of such systems, an integration of a

telemedicine would be necessary, where the automatic system can still provide services to people, doctors' interactions through the system will always be appreciated.

3.1 System architecture

It is known for many, that diagnosis use tools and readings that are case-dependent. Images and sounds can be used to early diagnosis of medical conditions. In this work, we will rely mainly on attached cameras and microphones of smartphones for recording. These recordings (readings) will be compared with a previously prepared dataset for possible diagnosis. To ensure further accuracy, the system has equipped with an additional feature, which will send the auto-diagnosis results along with person data to specialized doctor to further confirm or update the results. This feature is important for patient candidates as well as to improve the accuracy of the dataset. Figure 1 illustrates the system architecture.

Fig. 1. System Architecture

3.2 User registration and profile

The system will allow people to register either as patient candidate or as a doctor. Each of which has different user interface and unique privileges and features. When registration as a patient candidate, the system will ask the person to key-in some demographic information that would help in narrowing the search stage later. Age, sex, medical history and so on. While when a person registers as a doctor, the system will ask doctors to key-in their area of interest (specialization) or any future information that might help

in matching the right doctor with the case. It is worth to mention that, when registration as a doctor, an authentication step is required with the aid of the local health authority to ensure his/her claim. Figure 2 shows the diagram of registration.

Fig. 2. User registration and profile

3.3 Dataset

Since the proposed system is not tailored to diagnose a specific disease or group of related diseases, several datasets can be integrated to the system. Some can be adopted from trusted sources such as [15, 16], while other can be generated during the development phase of the system.

3.4 Implementation details

The system was built entirely using free and open source technologies. For the backend and the server components, an adoption to the PHP scripting language [17] along with MYSQL [18] as a database were used. While for the frontend and the mobile app languages, a Flutter [19], which a Google made framework, was adopted. This framework is a cross-platform mobile application development used to develop mobile application for iOS and Android.

The client/server communication is made through API calls initiated from the mobile or end-user for standardization purposes and ease of future integration. This feature will enable the possible integration from heterogeneous devices and not just smartphones as Flutter framework work for not only mobile devices but also for personal computers.

3.5 Privacy considerations

Privacy became a trending topic after the emergence of smartphones. Several studies have questioned people privacy while interacting with their handheld devices. In this study, a consideration has made by disallowing to any identity or personal information beyond person permission to send throughout the system. Apart, all communicating data are encrypted using 256-bit AES encryption algorithm [20].

4 Testing phase

a Functional testing is conducted. where a validation and black box testing to the software components are made. Registration component, personal authentication component, Application Programming Interfaces (APIs), database, and client/server communications all are tested and gave a high prevision outcome.

5 Conclusion and future aspects

In this work, a promising self and early disease diagnosis system using emerging technologies is presented. In contrary to other existing systems, the proposed system has considered auto-diagnosis along with typical telemedicine-based diagnosis by doctors. Preliminary results have shown promising outcomes. However, as a young system, there are still several angles to improve. Technically, for instance, doctors can send the case data to another specialist if he/she finds that the case requires someone else intervention or considering the app as a virtual medical identity and patient medical history.

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